

Magnetism and Molecular Structure : The Estimate of Metal-Nitrogen Bond Effect in Cadmium Chloride Complexes of Organic Bases

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Magnetic susceptibilities of a few complexes of cadmium chloride with organic bases have been measured and these values compared with their computed ones obtained from the experimental molar susceptibilities of the components. The deviations between the two sets of values have been discussed in the light of Van Vleck's equation for the molar susceptibility of polyatomic molecule. A comparison between the observed deviations in the present work with the corresponding zinc chloride complexes has been attempted.

In the previous investigation¹ magnetic susceptibilities of some complexes of zinc chloride with pyridine, quinoline, and aniline and its derivatives were measured with a view to ascertaining the nature of the metal-nitrogen bond in these complexes. In this communication investigation has been extended to the study of complexes of cadmium chloride with the same ligands.

EXPERIMENTAL

B. D. H. AnalaR grade cadmium chloride was used for the preparation of these complexes. The organic bases were of B. D. H. or Mercks' 'pure quality' and were further purified by distillation. The method of preparation of different complexes was the same as described earlier¹. Magnetic susceptibilities of these complexes and their component compounds were measured by a modified form of Gouy's balance, described by Prasad *et al.*² In Table I are presented the values of specific (χ) and molar susceptibilities (χ_m) of these complexes and their components, the values being expressed in -1×10^{-6} C. G. S. units.

DISCUSSION

For the sake of comparison, the molar magnetic susceptibilities of these complexes have been calculated from the knowledge of the observed values of the susceptibilities of their components, assuming strict additivity. Magnetic susceptibilities of organic ligands and cadmium chloride required for this purpose were measured by the authors in this laboratory. In the case of hydrated compounds, the molar susceptibility of the complex was

1. Sonalkar and Datar, in press. *J. Univ. Bombay*.
2. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1944, 20A, 224.

TABLE I

Compounds.	χ	χ_m (obs.)	χ_m (calc.)	$\Delta \chi_m$ ($\chi_m - \chi_m'$)	% $\Delta \chi_m$	$\rho \bar{\chi}$
1. Dipyridine-cadmium-chloride	0.457	156.00	164.73	-8.73	-5.60	..
Pyridine	0.593	46.92	..	..	..	5.24
2. Diquinoline-cadmium-chloride.	0.526	232.30	245.93	-13.63	-5.87	..
Quinoline	0.678	87.52	..	..	..	4.92
3. Dianilino-cadmium-chloride dihydrate.	0.511	207.20	216.93	-9.73	-4.69	..
Aniline	0.672	62.55	..	..	..	4.62
4. Ditoluidine-cadmium-chloride dihy- drate. (<i>ortho</i>)	0.546	236.50	240.91	-4.41	-1.86	..
Toluidine (<i>ortho</i>)	0.696	74.54	..	..	..	4.40
5. Ditoluidine-cadmium-chloride (<i>meta</i>)	0.503	199.90	219.69	-19.79	-9.90	..
Toluidine (<i>meta</i>)	0.695	74.40	..	..	..	4.68
6. Ditoluidine-cadmium-chloride (<i>para</i>).	0.515	204.70	216.05	-11.35	-5.60	..
Toluidine (<i>para</i>)	0.678	72.58	..	..	..	5.16
7. Dixylidine-cadmium-chloride (<i>meta</i>)	0.546	232.00	244.69	-12.69	-5.47	..
Xylidine (<i>meta</i>)	0.718	86.00	..	..	..	4.90
8. Cadmium chloride.	0.387	70.89	..	..	..	..

calculated by taking the susceptibility of water molecule as equal to the sum of the Pascal's constants for two atoms of hydrogen and one atom of oxygen ($\chi_m = 10.47$). The usual practice of using the observed value ($\chi_m = 12.96$) has been avoided for reasons stated in the previous paper¹. The computed values of the molar susceptibilities of the complexes are given in column 4 of the same table. The percentage deviation from additivity is given in the 6th column.

It is apparent from the results that the observed values are lower than their computed ones and therefore deviate from additivity. As Gouy's method gives results of 1% accuracy, these deviations are therefore quite significant.

According to Van Vleck, the susceptibility of a polar molecule in Σ state is given by the equation:

$$\chi_m = \chi_d + \chi_p$$

The decrease in molar susceptibility may be attributed to the changes in the χ_d and χ_p terms of the above equation. The χ_d term is a function of $\sum_i \bar{r}^3$ of all electrons in the molecule and the χ_p term represents the second order paramagnetism independent of temperature, which arises on account of the mixing of the ground and excited states of electrons in the molecule. If the metal-nitrogen bond in the complex is sufficiently strong, the associating units will come very close to the metal atom, thus decreasing the value of $\sum_i \bar{r}^3$ and hence that of the diamagnetic susceptibility of the molecule (χ_d). In addition, this type of bonding is also likely to affect the symmetry of the component molecule. If it is assumed that these complexes are similar to the diammine complexes of zinc with the formula $ZnCl_2 \cdot 2NH_3$, for which a tetrahedral structure has been established from the X-ray study²,

2. MacGillivray and Bijovet, *Z. Krist.*, 1936, 94, 249.

then this type of configuration involves the use of sp^3 orbitals of the metal atom. According to Pople⁴ the χ_p term, which affects both diamagnetic susceptibility and the nuclear magnetic resonance, shift is quite important when p orbitals are used for the bond formation. The use of sp^3 orbitals will therefore result in a significant contribution to the χ_p term and consequently a reduction in the molar susceptibility of the complex. The observed deviations from additivity may be ascribed to the changes in χ_d and χ_p terms resulting from the combination of the anhydrous salt with the ligands. Since χ_d and χ_p terms have opposite signs, the deviation from additivity is the net result of the two opposing effects. The change in the χ_p term would be more significant since the symmetry of the complex may be entirely different from that of the constituent molecules.

The strength of the bond between metal and nitrogen depends on the electronegativity of nitrogen of the ligand molecule. The greater the basicity of the ligand, the stronger should be the bond and hence the greater would be the deviation from additivity. Since pK values of ligands indicate electronegativity of nitrogen in different ligands, an attempt was made to correlate observed deviations with pK values of the corresponding ligands. The pK values taken from the literature are recorded in Table I.

From the results it is not possible to trace a regular relation between pK values and the observed deviations. This is partly because of the fact that the complexes of aniline and *o*-toluidine contain water molecules but others do not. If these complexes are octahedral, one would expect a much less contribution due to second order paramagnetism as compared to the tetrahedral complexes, as the octahedron is more symmetrical than the tetrahedron. Comparison of the results of *m*-toluidine with *o*-toluidine supports this inference.

A comparison of the observed values of percentage deviations from additivity between the complex of cadmium chloride and zinc chloride reported previously⁴, is very interesting.

TABLE II

Associating ligands	% Deviation from additivity for complexes of	
	ZnCl ₂	CdCl ₂
1. Pyridine	-8.30	-5.60
2. Quinoline	-11.19	-5.87
3. Aniline	-7.95	-4.69
4. <i>o</i> -Toluidine	-5.49	-1.88
5. <i>m</i> -Toluidine	-10.27	-9.90
6. <i>p</i> -Toluidine	-8.04	-5.60
7. <i>m</i> -Xylidine	-11.81	-5.47

An examination of the results indicate that the complexes of Zn show much larger and more negative deviations in susceptibility than the corresponding complexes of Cd. This means that the formation of zinc chloride complexes results in greater diminution in susceptibility than that of cadmium chloride with the same ligands. Since these deviations are related to the strength of metal-nitrogen bond, from the trend of the results one is led

4. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1957, **239A**, 451.

to the conclusion that the bond between Zn and the ligand is much stronger than that between Cd and the ligand. One would therefore expect that the complexes of zinc would be more stable than the complexes of cadmium. A search in the literature for the data on the stability constants for these complexes was not fruitful. Only the data for the complexes of pyridine are available. This solitary data show that the stability of cadmium complex with pyridine is greater than that of zinc with pyridine. The inconsistency observed between magnetic susceptibility and stability may probably be due to the fact that the data on stability have been obtained from the measurements on solution and therefore may not be strictly comparable to the deviation observed in the present investigation which has been carried out on solids.

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